

D3.5. Testing of arrays, pump and image formation electronics for image quality and required enhancements

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D3.5 Description

The deliverable is the output of the work done within task T3.5, which aims to test developed ultrasound data acquisition unit (probes + electronics). The unit will be tested by using calibrated phantoms with acoustic and mechanical properties close to human tissue. TELEMED has tools for quantitative assessment of ultrasound image quality (measurements of spatial resolution, contrast resolution, and sensitivity). These tools will allow iterative feedback for image quality improvements.

D3.5 is planned as a report detailing the results of testing the ThrombUS+ ultrasound prototypes developed in WP3 and required image quality improvements.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AFE	Analogue front-end
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDUS	Compression Duplex Ultrasound
CHI	Central Hub & Intelligence Module
CNR	Contrast-to-noise ratio
CSW	C-shell type Semirigid Wearable
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EAC	Electronic Actuator Controller
FWHM	Full width at half maximum
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GUI	Graphical user interface
ITHI	Inverse tissue harmonic imaging
LG	Lateral Gap
MG	Medial Gap
MI	Mechanical Index
ScNR	Speckle-to-noise ratio
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
USM	ThrombUS+ Ultrasound module
WAM	Wearable actuator module

Executive Summary

This document presents the evaluation of the newly developed ThrombUS+ ultrasound probes and their integration with the beamformer system. The evaluation included spectral measurements, signal-to-noise ratio assessments, and imaging capability tests using calibrated phantoms that simulate human tissue properties. Quantitative image quality metrics such as spatial resolution, contrast resolution, and sensitivity were utilized to understand and benchmark system performance.

Overall, the conclusions of the evaluation show that the probes, once integrated into the USM imaging system, demonstrated promising imaging characteristics and reliable performance across the tested parameters. The iterative optimization process led to noticeable improvements in image quality and diagnostic capabilities. The results suggest that the evaluated ultrasound unit meets the required standards for quality imaging and is suitable for further clinical studies and validation.

1. Ultrasound probes developed by VERMON and FRAUNHOFER

Ultrasound probes developed by VERMON (conventional technology) and FRAUNHOFER (CMUT-based technology) were integrated with TELEMED's software and the beamformers. At first stage, probe characteristics (geometry and frequency responses) provided by the manufacturer were analysed to properly address individual properties of each transducer array. The figure below depicts probes provided by FRAUNHOFER (probe code AC1655, pictures adapted from¹) and VERMON (pictures adapted from²) and the corresponding amplitude spectra for both probes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Top left: CMUT-based probe AC1655 developed by FRAUNHOFER. Top right: averaged amplitude spectrum of probe AC1655. Bottom left: Linear array (LA6.0/128) developed by VERMON. Bottom right: frequency response of probe LA6.0/128

Initial comparison of the frequency contents of both probes showed that probe LA6.0/128 can operate at higher frequencies. The central frequency of AC1655 is approximately 4.3 MHz, while for LA6.0/128 it is 6.3 MHz, and it also has a wider bandwidth. This feature could be an important factor when selecting a probe for clinical experiments. The frequency response characteristics provided served as input data for further tuning of probes with TELEMED's beamformers.

¹ Völz U., Kircher M., Lange N., Ultrasound Transducer Prototypes: MEMS Technology, Deliverable 3.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 02 January 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540400>

² Legros M, Pousset N, Toffesi Sieve S, Boulay S, Voisin D, Raybaud G, Deliverable 3.1, Ultrasound Transducer Array Prototypes: Composite PZT technology, Deliverable 3.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 2 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500724>

2. Probe integration and beamformer optimization procedure

The standard procedure implemented by TELEMED for the integration process encompasses both physical and software-level adaptation, including transducer pin mapping, software interfacing, and beamformer parameter tuning to ensure optimal performance. The integration workflow is primarily iterative and aims to determine the optimal beamformer configuration for each transducer. This includes defining excitation pulse characteristics, tuning analogue front-end (AFE) parameters, and optimizing receive filter settings. The procedure may be summarized as follows:

- **Frequency Selection:** A discrete set of transmit frequencies is selected in accordance with the frequency response specifications provided by the transducer manufacturer. Typically, 3 to 5 frequencies are chosen to accommodate varying patient anatomies: lower frequencies for enhanced penetration in deeper tissues and higher frequencies for improved spatial resolution.
- **Parameter Adjustment per Frequency:** For each selected frequency, the following parameters are tuned:
 1. Excitation Pulse Configuration: Adjustment of the number of pulse periods to ensure efficient transducer excitation.
 2. Receive Band-Pass Filter Settings: Optimization of the central frequency and bandwidth to align with the selected transmit frequency.
 3. Analogue Front-End Parameters: Fine-tuning of gain/filtering settings within the receive chain.
- **Quantitative Image Quality Assessment:** Acquired images are evaluated using quantitative image quality metrics to assess the efficacy of the current parameter set.
- **Iterative Refinement:** If the image quality assessment indicates potential for further improvement, additional iterations of parameter adjustment are performed.

The goal of this procedure is to achieve optimal imaging performance for each transducer model, ensuring compatibility with TELEMED's imaging systems and delivering quality diagnostic output.

3. Probe AC1655 integration and USM imaging testing results

Experiments were performed in two stages: 1) spectral measurements and 2) evaluation of imaging capabilities by using CIRS tissue mimicking phantom (model 040GSE) Additionally used: EchoWave II 4.3.1b48 software for image acquisition, Drivers 2.30b30 and Artus RF Data Control 2.2.2 for signal acquisition.

3.1. Measurements of spectra

Spectral measurements were carried out in a water tank by observing the reflections from a steel plate, the transmit focal depth set approximately to that spot (4 cm depth) (Figure 2). The signals were recorded directly after the beamformer, prior to digital band-pass filtering.

FRAUNHOFER's probe AC1655 was excited at three different frequencies (4, 5, 7 MHz). The resulting normalised spectra (normalised by the global maxima of all three spectra) are shown in Figure 3. The probe AC1655 demonstrates optimal operation at an excitation frequency of 4 MHz. At excitation frequencies of 5 MHz and 7 MHz, only minimal frequency spectrum shift to the right was observed, accompanied by an approximately 20% reduction in amplitude.

Subsequently, ultrasound module (USM) in conjunction with the AC1655 probe was compared to the commercially available TELEMED based phased array probe P5-1S15-A6, which exhibits similar documented spectral characteristics and has similar element pitch. The comparison of the normalised spectra of both probes (Figure 4) indicates that the bandwidth of P5-1S15-A6 is marginally broader; however, AC1655 possesses a slightly higher central frequency. Overall, the two probes are comparable concerning their frequency content.

Figure 2. Experimental setup: Water tank with immersed steel plate and AC1655 probe (left). Experimental software Artus RF Data control 2.2.2 GUI front panel (right).

Figure 3. Normalized spectra of the reflection signal from steel plate at different electrical excitation frequencies.

Figure 4. Comparison of frequency spectra of probes AC1655 and P5-1S15-A6.

3.2. Signal-to-noise ratio measurements

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was estimated for probes AC1655 and P5-1S15-A6 before image quality assessment. SNR was estimated for both probes using equation [1]:

$$SNR = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{A_S}{A_N} \right) \quad [1]$$

where, A_S : mean amplitude of signal envelope at the reflection; and A_N : mean amplitude of envelope signal at the noisy region). Figure 5 presents obtained signals together with detected radiofrequency signal data envelope (peak is the reflection from steel plate).

Figure 5. Obtained signals together with detected radiofrequency signal data envelope for probes AC1655 and P5-1S15-A6 (legend presents SNR results).

The estimated SNR for the AC1655 probe was 29.55 dB, while for the probe P5-1S15-A6, it was 41.78 dB. Probe AC1655 has a higher signal amplitude under the same conditions; however, the noise level is higher as well.

3.3. Assessment of imaging capabilities using AC1655 probe

In the final stage, the imaging capabilities of AC1655 were assessed. The evaluation of image quality was conducted utilising a tissue-mimicking phantom model GSE040 with embedded targets, produced by CIRS³. The front panel of the phantom and an associated photograph are presented below in Figure 6.

The vertical distance group marked by the red rectangle was used to assess spatial resolution, while the grey scale targets marked by the yellow rectangle were used to evaluate contrast (Figure 6; left). Structural reflections from the phantom background served for sensitivity measurements.

The AC1655 probe was utilised in two scanning modalities: as a linear probe and as a sector phased array to broaden the field of view. Linear scans were compared with the commercially available TELEMED L12-5N40-A4 probe, while phased array scans were compared to the TELEMED P5-1S15-A6 phased array probe. All probes were operated at a frequency of 4 MHz. Figure 7 illustrates comparison images obtained from phantom evaluations using the AC1655 probe in both linear and sector scanning modes, alongside images from conventional TELEMED off-the-shelf probes (linear L12-5N40-A4 and phased array P5-1S15-A6).

³ Computerized Imaging Reference Systems, Inc, recently acquired by Sun Clear, a Mirion Technologies Inc. medical company <https://www.sunuclear.com/>

Figure 6. Front panel (left) and photo (right) of the CIRS phantom used for objective imaging quality assessment.

Figure 7. Imaging capabilities assessment compared images obtained by using AC1655 probe and different scan types (linear (top) and sector (bottom)) and TELEMED's on-the-shelf probes L12-5N40-A4 and P5-1S15-A6.

The comparison revealed a limited penetration of the AC1655 probe, with penetration measurements falling below 40 mm, which is inadequate for visualising deep veins. Meanwhile, for the linear commercially available high-frequency probe L12-5N40-A4, which is based on conventional technology and operates at the same 4 MHz frequency, the penetration depth exceeds 60 mm. Images obtained with the AC1655 probe displayed relatively strong secondary reflections in proximity to the primary reflectors, characterised by elongated tails of the reflections. Structural reflections were comparable across different probe types. Overall, the AC1655 probe exhibits greater potential for phased array applications, as its 64 small elements

produce a narrow linear scan. Because of the limited sensitivity and capability to operate at different frequencies probe AC1655 was not investigated further.

4. Probe LA6.0/128 integration and USM imaging testing results

The ultrasound data acquisition unit, which includes the beamformer and probe manufactured by VERMON, initially selected excitation frequencies of 4.5, 7.5, and 9 MHz. The aim was to find an optimal balance between resolution and penetration. Preliminary assessment involves analysing the frequency spectra of signals reflected from a steel plate in a water tank.

4.1. Measurements of spectra

The selection of frequency facilitates a balance between penetration and resolution. Penetration capability is particularly crucial for subjects with greater thigh diameters, whereas for more typical cases, higher frequencies such as 7.5 MHz and 9 MHz may be employed to achieve superior resolution. RF signals used for spectral comparison were captured utilising the TELEMED Artus RF Data Control 2.2.2 software, observing reflections from a steel plate (as depicted in Figure 8) with the transmit focal depth approximately aligned to the specified location at 4 cm depth. These signals were captured directly after the beamformer, prior to digital band-pass filtering.

Figure 8. Experimental setup, probe immersed into water tank orthogonally to the steel plate (left). Experimental software Artus RF Data Control 2.2.2 GUI front panel (right).

Obtained spectra at different electrical excitation frequency are presented below (Figure 9).

Spectral assessment indicated that the loss in sensitivity exceeds the improvement in resolution between 7.5 and 9 MHz excitation frequencies; therefore, an additional iteration is required to fine-tune the set of frequencies and to optimize the beamformer parameters. Consequently, the set of frequencies was modified to 5 MHz, 7 MHz, and 9 MHz in the second iteration.

Figure 9. Normalized amplitude spectra (normalized by global maxima) for different electrical excitation pulses (at 4.5 MHz, 7.5 MHz and 9 MHz).

4.2. LA6.0/128 array imaging capabilities assessment

Imaging capabilities were evaluated using the same tissue mimicking phantom 040GSE (by CIRS) as presented in Chapter 3.3.

4.3. Sensitivity (penetration ability) measurement method

The measurement is based on methodology for low-contrast penetration measurement proposed by Gibson et al⁴. Two images, acquired with a fixed probe, are required for the measurement. The operator selects a region of interest (ROI) at the centre of the image, ensuring that it is free of test objects (such as point reflectors or objects used for contrast measurements), and that the B-mode image contains only speckle and electronic noise.

The images captured under the fixed probe condition differ in their electronic noise component (with speckle remaining identical), which can be estimated by calculating the difference between the two images. Two images must be derived from the ROI, one by summing each pair of corresponding pixels in the two captured images and another by taking the difference. These new images are divided into windows [window size 3 X 11 pixels], and the standard deviation of pixel values in each, $\sigma_{SUM}(i)$ and $\sigma_{DIFF}(i)$ for the i -th window, calculated. From these, the standard deviation of speckle, $\sigma_S(i)$, and that of noise, $\sigma_N(i)$, are calculated from equations [2] and [3]:

$$\sigma_N(i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sigma_{DIFF}(i) \tag{2}$$

$$\sigma_S(i) = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\sigma_{SUM}^2(i) - \sigma_{DIFF}^2(i)}. \tag{3}$$

Thus, profiles of speckle and noise standard deviation against depth are derived. A speckle-to-noise-amplitude ratio, $ScNR(i)$, was derived by taking a ratio of the two profiles (equation [4]):

$$ScNR(i) = \frac{\sigma_S(i)}{\sigma_N(i)}. \tag{4}$$

⁴ Gibson NM, Dudley NJ, Griffith K. A computerised quality control testing system for B-mode ultrasound. *Ultrasound Med Biol.* 2001 Dec;27(12):1697-711. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-5629\(01\)00479-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-5629(01)00479-3).

The depth at which $ScNR(i)$ fell below a threshold value are taken as the penetration depth (sensitivity). In our case the threshold was set to 2.

4.4. Sensitivity measurement results

Sensitivity measurement results before and after beamformer parameters retuning are presented in Table 1 with respect to different electrical excitation frequencies.

Table 1. Sensitivity measurement results (2 iterations, initial set of frequencies marked by red colour, and optimized set of frequencies of electrical excitation allowed to select for the USM 5, 7 and 9 MHz, green colour).

	1 st iteration				2 nd iteration			
Excitation frequency (MHz)	4.5	7.5	9	4.5 ITHI*	5	7	9	5 ITHI*
Sensitivity (mm)	64.26	59.58	59.58	53.47	64.91	62.89	56.18	53.80

*ITHI – inverse tissue harmonic imaging.

The measurement results demonstrated an anticipated inverse correlation between excitation frequency and penetration depth. The achieved depths, which are slightly less than 6 cm in the most adverse case, should be adequate for the majority of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) cases. For subjects with larger thigh diameters, lower frequencies (such as 7 MHz or 5 MHz) could be employed. Optimization iterations enhanced sensitivity across all tested scenarios by a few percent.

4.5. Spatial resolution measurements method

Spatial resolution measurement is a well-established method, and therefore, it is not described in detail herein. In general, it evaluates the Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of a point reflector observed within an ultrasound image, as detected by a peak detector, in both axial and lateral directions. The correlation between axial or lateral resolution and depth can be determined using phantoms equipped with arranged point reflectors. An illustrative example of the measurement principle is presented in Figure 10. The left image displays detected peaks corresponding to point reflectors, while the right image provides a one-dimensional view of a single point, with the full width at half maximum (FWHM) level marked.

Figure 10. Spatial resolution measurement principle. Left: B mode image together with detected point reflectors. Right: measurement principle of spatial resolution (FWHM – full width at half maximum).

4.6. Spatial resolution measurements results

Axial resolution measurement results before and after beamformer parameters retuning are presented in Table 2 with respect to different electrical excitation frequencies.

Table 2. Axial resolution measurement results (2 iterations, initial set of frequencies marked by red colour, and optimized set of frequencies at 5, 7 and 9 MHz, marked with red colour).

	1 st iteration				2 nd iteration			
Excitation frequency (MHz)	4.5	7.5	9	4.5 ITHI*	5	7	9	5 ITHI*
Axial resolution (mm)	0.76	0.51	0.63	0.45	0.78	0.58	0.57	0.51

*Resolutions measured taking average value of 4 or 5 measurement points at different imaging depths

Lateral resolution measurement results before and after beamformer parameters retuning are presented in Table 3 with respect to different electrical excitation frequencies.

Table 3. Lateral resolution measurement results (2 iterations, initial set of frequencies marked by red colour, and optimized set of frequencies at 5, 7, and 9 MHz, marked with red colour).

	1 st iteration				2 nd iteration			
Excitation frequency (MHz)	4.5	7.5	9	4.5 ITHI*	5	7	9	5 ITHI*
Lateral resolution (mm)	1.54	1.14	1.21	1.07	1.52	1.12	1.12	0.87

*Resolutions measured taking average value of 4 or 5 measurement points at different imaging depths

In conclusion, lateral resolution was enhanced in all instances, albeit at the expense of some axial resolution, which is inherently high. Lateral resolution is dependent on probe geometry and focusing quality; therefore, it is considerably more challenging to improve than axial resolution.

4.7. Contrast measurements method

Contrast measurement is predicated on the well-established parameter within the image processing community known as the contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR). An operator manually delineates a circular object distinct from the background, thereby obtaining the object region. The background region is subsequently extracted automatically, encompassing a region wider by 10 pixels than the radius of the circular object. An example illustrating the measurement principle is provided in Figure 11.

The ratio is calculated using equation [5]:

$$CNR = \frac{I_{object} - I_{background}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{object}^2 + \sigma_{background}^2}} \quad [5]$$

where I_{object} and $I_{background}$ are mean intensities in the object and background regions respectively, σ^2 – denotes variance (for the object and background intensities). If the object and background exhibit identical mean

intensities, the Contrast-to-Noise Ratio (CNR) will be zero. Should the background be brighter than the object, the CNR will be negative; conversely, it will be positive in all other cases.

Figure 11. Selected regions of interest (ROIs) for assessing contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR).

4.8. Contrast measurement results

Contrast was measured for the brighter than the background object (+ 6 dB). CNR measurement results before and after beamformer parameters retuning are presented in Table 4 with respect to different electrical excitation frequencies.

Table 4. CNR measurement results (2 iterations, initial set of frequencies marked by red colour, and optimized set of frequencies at 5, 7, and 9 MHz, marked with red colour).

	1 st iteration				2 nd iteration			
Excitation frequency (MHz)	4.5	7.5	9	4.5 ITHI*	5	7	9	5 ITHI*
CNR	1.23	1.23	1.05	1.02	1.39	1.28	1.10	0.98

In conclusion CNR parameter showed improvement after beamformer parameter retuning in all except the inverse harmonics case.

4.9. Reference B-mode phantom images obtained in the experiments

Figure 12 shows images acquired during the two iterations of the image quality assessment for reference, for the various selected frequencies.

Image comparison reveals the improvement of sensitivity and generally better-quality phantom images after optimization of the beamformer parameters.

Figure 12. B mode images obtained before and after optimization at different electrical excitation frequencies.

Figure 13. Photo of Doppler flow phantom used for the colour flow mode sensitivity assessment.

4.10. Colour Doppler sensitivity measurement method

A Colour Doppler sensitivity test was conducted using Doppler phantom 523A (see Figure 13). The measurement of Colour Doppler sensitivity was performed at the depth at which flow imaging data could still be reliably identified.

4.11. Colour Doppler sensitivity measurement results

The obtained sensitivity was >60 mm, which is depth below statistical depth of veins under investigation. Experimental image of Doppler phantom is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Colour Doppler sensitivity test result.

4.12. USM acoustic and thermal characterization

The ultrasound module (TELEMED's beamformer + probe developed by VERMON) underwent acoustic and thermal characterization tests for safety. A series of on-site acoustic and thermal characterizations were conducted for the ultrasound data acquisition unit in conjunction with a 128-element linear array probe developed by VERMON.

Acoustic output measurements were performed using the Acertara⁵ Acoustic Measurement System (AMS) with a calibrated bilaminar PVDF hydrophone. Testing covered B-mode, M-mode, and Colour Doppler (CD) operational modes. Measurements were conducted across five transmit focal depths (10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 mm) and for all available transmit frequencies in B-mode and M-mode, as well as both available transmit frequencies in Colour Doppler mode.

The results confirmed that the measured acoustic output parameters—Mechanical Index (MI) and Spatial Peak Temporal Average Intensity (Ispta.3)—remained within the limits defined by regulatory guidelines:

- MI < 1.9,
- Ispta.3 < 720 mW/cm².

This compliance was verified across all evaluated system settings and operational combinations.

⁵ Acertara Acoustic Laboratories, LLC, <https://acertaralabs.com/>

Thermal assessment of transducer surface heating was conducted using a calibrated thermal phantom (model 754-02) and a digital thermometer equipped with a type T thermocouple.

Results demonstrated that the transducer surface temperature increase during simulated use (thermal phantom) did not exceed 27°C above ambient, and the absolute temperature in still air did not exceed 50°C, in accordance with safety limits defined in IEC 60601-2-37.

The characterization was performed in accordance with TELEMED's internal procedures harmonized with the requirements of IEC 60601-2-37:2024.

A complete IEC 60601-2-37:2024-compliant test report, including full data tables and documentation for all configurations, was not produced due to the extensive time required to compile it. Source data files are available.

5. High level testing of wearable actuator and ultrasound modules integration

Following probe and beamformer integration and image quality assessment and enhancement by TELEMED, KTU focused on integrating the prototype ultrasound module (USM) (without AI) and the wearable actuator module (WAM). Subsequently, integration testing based on the testing methodology defined in D6.2⁶ was followed. The tests cases and their respective outcomes (based on Table 2, from deliverable D6.2) are presented in Table 5. For details regarding individual test cases, refer to the respective chapter below.

Table 5. Results of high-level readiness testing of ultrasound (USM) and wearable actuator module integration.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results	Outcome
1	Compression Duplex Ultrasound method is initialized by pressing the "Start" button in the GUI. The SDK from the ultrasound sends a command to start image acquisition.	TC_CDUS_01	SR_PR01_USM_08	Image acquisition can be started utilizing ultrasound's SDK.	Pass. Figure 31 A and B, Technical GUI button "Run".
2.1	USM starts streaming images to the computer (technical GUI).	TC_CDUS_02	SR_PR01_USM_17	Images can be sent to computer (GUI) utilizing ultrasound's SDK.	Pass. Figure 31, grayscale image in top-left of Technical GUI.
2.1	USM starts streaming images to the computer (technical GUI).	TC_CDUS_02	SR_PR01_USM_17	Images can be sent to computer (GUI) utilizing ultrasound's SDK.	Pass. Figure 31, grayscale image in top-left of Technical GUI.
2.2	Synchronously with each acquired frame, USM sends	TC_CDUS_03	SR_PR01_USM_05	Trigger signals are sent to the compression	Pass. Is equal number of data points sampled

⁶ A., Jucevičius M., Daukantas S., Lukoševičius A., Eitminavičius R., Jurkonis R., Balling S., Querengässer J., Maja S., Vehkaoja A., Prinz T., Portokallidis N., Didaskalou S., Marozas V., Kaldoudi E., Testing methodology and test plan, Deliverable D6.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 30 June 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15769783>.

	synchronization signal to WAM, so it can synchronize pressure measurements to images.			actuator from the ultrasound.	from pressure sensor and calculated strain estimates from image. See Figures 30 and 31.
5	The GUI receives these outputs and sends the "Start_Inflation" command to the WAM using the WAM SDK.	TC_CDUS_04	SR_PR01_WAM_02 SR_PR01_WAM_04 SR_PR01_WAM_06 SR_PR01_WAM_08	Inflation can be initialized via WAM's SDK.	Pass. Figure 31 B, button "Quick Set" in tab Pump Controls of Technical GUI.
6	WAM starts inflation and starts either periodically (if a sync signal is received) or on demand, sending pressure values to the GUI, for pressuring monitoring.	TC_CDUS_05	SR_PR01_WAM_06	Current pressure levels are returned from the WAM to the computer (GUI) via the SDK.	Pass. Figure 30 A, current pressures are indicated in numerical indicator #PRESS. Example is 119.520000,118.47005 in tab Pump Controls Technical GUI. The other example in Figure 31 B.
9	Based on strain measurements, or maximum allowed pressure, the GUI send the "Stop_Inflation" command to WAM, if predefined thresholds have been reached.	TC_CDUS_06	SR_PR01_WAM_06	Terminate inflation signal can be sent to the WAM, via it's SDK, upon user's request or upon maximum allowed pressure levels are reached.	Pass. Figure 30 A, pressure diagram indicate saturation around 120mmHg in accordance with target of pressure at 120mmHg. Button in red colour "STOP" is dedicated to initializing decompression in tab Pump Controls Technical GUI.
10	The GUI terminates the image acquisition by sending the "STOP" command to the USM, finalizing the CDUS method.	TC_CDUS_07	SR_PR01_USM_17	Upon receiving the "STOP" command from the computer (GUI), ultrasound terminates image acquisition and stops triggering the WAM.	Pass. Figure 30, button of blue colour "Freeze" in Technical GUI.

5.1. Implementation of CDUS method

From the preliminary laboratory testing, evidence was obtained regarding the recommended application of the ultrasound probe on the thigh, for implementing the compression duplex ultrasound method (CDUS). An incremental hardware version is shown in several photos (Figure 15).

Figure 15. ThrombUS+ prototypes for compression duplex ultrasound. Left: The body-mounted part is separated from the electronic air-pumping and ultrasonic imaging modules. Top-right: The ultrasonic imaging transducer is applied to the medial-front side of the thigh, while the air bladder is applied to the back-lateral side. Mid-right: The pneumatic tubing and multichannel cable. The electronic boards are designed to be powered and controlled via USB-C interfaces. Bottom-right: the wearable part while not worn.

The wearable part includes an ultrasonic imaging transducer supported by a C-shell semi-rigid wearable (CSW) structure, which also houses an air bladder. The structure of the wearable component and mounting on corresponding anatomy⁷ of thigh is shown in Figure 16.

The C-shell semi-rigid wearable (CSW) consists of two C-shells: the green C-shell supports the ultrasound array transducer, while the blue C-shell holds the air bladder (Figure 16). The length of both the green arc

⁷ Ginard I. Henry, Grant M. Kleiber, Comprehensive lower extremity anatomy, <https://plasticsurgerykey.com/comprehensive-lower-extremity-anatomy/>.

and the blue arc (which supports the rectangular bladder) is 21 cm each. The air bladder has a width of 12 cm, which is also the width of the green C-shell that holds the transducer.

Mounting of the CSW on the thigh is recommended with respect to the anatomical location of the femoral vessels. The ultrasound array transducer, shown as a green rectangle, is positioned to face the femoral vein and artery in the adductor canal (Hunter’s canal). The application site of the air bladder (blue arc) is positioned on the back-lateral side of the thigh.

Relative to the CSW holding the imaging transducer, two gaps are identified: the lateral gap (LG), located on the outer side of the thigh, and the medial gap (MG), located on the inner side (Figure 16).

Subject body positioning might change soft tissues response to compression, and especial attention was considered when muscles tissues are in the site of interest on thigh. Standing position was not considered as the muscles activity is hard to suspend. Motion-less keeping of the leg in sitting pose is easier but could be challenging to completely relax muscles of thigh.

Figure 16. Structure of the wearable components with recommended mounting on the right thigh ⁸.
 LG: lateral gap; MG: medial gap.

Most beneficial body positions were under experimental investigation. CDUS method prototype was kept on the same location of thigh (Figure 17). The ultrasound transducer is shown in green, the air bladder in blue.

Figure 17. Body positioning to record thigh tissue and femoral vein response with the compression ultrasonography method (adapted from ⁹).

⁸ Chapter 2: Anterior and Medial Compartments of the Thigh in Thieme Dissector Volume 2: Abdomen and Lower Limb (Thieme Dissector, 2), 2022, 2nd Edition by Vishram Singh, ISBN:9789392819179; <https://anatomy.thieme.in/pdf/Chapter-2-%28Dissector-Vol.-II%29-with-watermark.pdf>.

⁹ Low Fowlers Position <https://animalia-life.club/qa/pictures/low-fowlers-position>

Clinical studies A protocol¹⁰ and experimental laboratory testing evidence shows that the compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method can be feasibly implemented by positioning the body in a supine position with the back elevated. This posture is considered optimal for patient comfort and is particularly beneficial for the application of the compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method.

A series of laboratory trials of the CDUS method were conducted on healthy subjects via a study involving 30 healthy volunteers. The study was approved by the Kaunas Region Biomedical Research Ethics Committee (No. BE-2-67).

For each subject, the C-shell semi-rigid wearable (CSW) was mounted, and a session of compression ultrasonography was performed. Adequate vessel patterns were observed and the femoral vein responded to compression. Before removing the CSW, the medial (MG) and lateral (LG) gaps were measured using a centimetre tape. The recorded measurements are presented in Figure 18

Figure 18. Overview of the gaps between the air bladder and the imaging transducer support in relation to thigh size.

This diagram illustrates the recommended location for applying the air bladder. Notably, as the circumference of the thigh increases, only the lateral gap (LG) needs to be adjusted accordingly. The increase in the lateral gap is almost directly proportional to the increase in thigh circumference.

The total duration of wearing the actuator module (WAM) on the thigh was two hours. Subjects did not report any intolerable tightness in the thigh tissues during compression. Each subject underwent approximately 9–12 compression sessions over the two-hour period. Half of the sessions were conducted in a sitting position, and the other half in a semi-recumbent (low Fowler's) position. Only the left thigh responses to compression were recorded.

Based on these preliminary results, semi-flexible edges were implemented in the C-shell semi-rigid wearable CSW to improve comfort and better support the WAM on the human thigh.

¹⁰ Clinical Study A – Ultrasound Data Collection Manual, <https://app.thrombus.eu/studies/a>

5.2. Tissue compression and vein reaction results *in-vivo*

With the currently available hardware for implementing the compression duplex ultrasound method (CDUS), tissue compression was performed on healthy volunteers in laboratory settings, and imaging data were collected. Two reference images, acquired during compression, are presented in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Example images from a sequence of *in-vivo* tissue ultrasonography. Left: frame #3 at the initializing of the compression duplex ultrasonography session. Right: frame #141 during the compression ultrasonography session, showing tissue reaction to compression.

In the adductor canal of the thigh of this example subject, the femoral artery and vein were located at depths ranging from 14 to 27 mm. The ultrasonic array transducer was mounted according to the recommendations described in Section 5.1, so the vessel patterns were observed in the central width of the ultrasonography B-mode image. The preferred B-mode imaging settings—depth of 60 mm and width of 40 mm—were consistent across the tested group of healthy individuals. In the total group of 30 healthy subjects, thigh circumference ranged from 46 cm to 59 cm, and in all cases, the femoral vessel structures were visible within the 60 x 40 mm B-mode image.

The extracted responses of the vein lumen from these images are presented in Figure 20. This figure demonstrates how the vein lumen responds to tissue compression, shown through diagrams of lumen vertical size and lumen area plotted against both applied pressure and strain.

The entire compression process was captured as a sequence of B-mode ultrasound images. Tissue response was characterized using a strain vs. time diagram (Figure 20A; Top). In this example, compression was applied continuously for 20 seconds, during which the tissue strain reached up to 8%. The interframe interval was approximately 0.12 seconds (~8Hz), resulting in a sequence of 200 images capturing the full progression of compression.

To analyse vessel structure response, specific images were selected from the sequence at representative levels of strain. Images with indexes 43, 99, 107, 118, 132, and 198 were extracted and are presented in Figure 20B for visual inspection and assessment of morphological changes.

The decrease in vein lumen size was estimated manually by marking the vertical and horizontal dimensions at the edges of the vein walls.

Figure 20. Example of in-vivo tissue compression and characterized responses of the vein in-vivo.

The area of the vein lumen was estimated by calculating the area of an ellipse using both the vertical and horizontal dimensions. In this example, the vertical size of the vein decreased from 11 mm to 4 mm. However, the change in lumen area was even more significant, reducing from approximately 80 mm² to less than 10 mm². This example illustrates that the deformation of the vein lumen may not occur equally in the vertical and horizontal directions. Therefore, quantifying vein response based on lumen area is considered more accurate and representative.

Not all vein responses were analysed in detail, as only manual segmentation algorithms were used. The implementation of AI-based models and automated analysis of the collected data is planned for future work packages, once the hardware and software components are fully integrated and orchestrated by the Central Hub and Intelligence (CHI).

Manual segmentation of *in-vivo* vein lumen reduction to 100% collapse (full closure) across the 30 subjects showed an average group pressure of 82 mmHg, with individual subject values ranging between 43 mmHg and 130 mmHg.

Additionally, the performance of the wearable actuator module (WAM) and the electronic actuator controller (EAC) for bladder inflation was evaluated across subjects with different body types and thigh circumferences.

ThromBUS+ clinical partners collected thigh circumference data from the first 511 patients enrolled in the ThromBUS+ Study A (Figure 21). The average thigh circumference was 56 cm, with a median of 53 cm, a standard deviation of 14 cm, a minimum of 35 cm, and a maximum of 110 cm. Data recorded during the KTU trial with healthy subjects showed that the enrolled volunteers had thigh circumferences ranging from 46 cm to 59 cm. Extracting the same range (44 cm–59 cm) from the patient data across all clinical sites, indicates that the compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method hardware would fit and function properly on 312 patients, representing 61% of all patients in Study A.

Figure 21. Statistics on the thigh size of the first 511 patients enrolled in ThrombUS+ Study A as of end of June 2025.

The feasibility of performing automated monitoring of *in-vivo* soft tissues in healthy volunteers was also explored. Although an AI-driven model for automated vein lumen characterization has not yet been implemented, the strain parameter alone could be used to characterize possible changes in the overall soft tissues of the thigh. The compression induction diagrams and *in-vivo* tissue responses are provided in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Results of an in-vivo monitoring trial on a researcher’s thigh. Left: time-pressure diagram showing the rate of pressure increase. Right: pressure-strain diagram showing thigh tissue response to compression.

These diagrams show the tissue response monitoring results from a single subject. The monitoring duration was 48 minutes, during which 22 compression sessions were performed on the thigh. The 10 × 22 cm rectangular air bladder in the WAM was inflated with air from the electronic actuator controller (EAC). The EAC controller powered a piezoelectric air pump with 1000 mW output, inflating the bladder to a target

pressure of 80 mmHg. All 22 recordings showed a final pressure within the range of 77–83 mmHg (see Figure 22; left).

The thigh compressions were uniform, with each pressurizing phase lasting 15 seconds. However, the soft tissue responses, expressed as pressure-strain diagrams (see Figure 22; right), were less uniform than the pressure-time diagrams representing the compression cycles. The family of pressure-strain curves shows a wider spread compared to the more consistent time-pressure curves.

The very first soft tissue response (dashed bold line) exhibited a weaker modulation of strain during compression. All subsequent compressions resulted in larger modulations of the strain parameter. This phenomenon of a reduced initial strain response was observed only in one subject's thigh. The researcher conducted these observations on himself over three different days and consistently noted this peculiarity of weaker strain response to the very first compression of the thigh soft tissue.

This intra-subject variance in recorded responses raises concerns about the potentially high inter-subject variance. Variability in anthropometric data and body constitution poses challenges for identifying stable and uniform objects necessary for testing the repeatability and robustness of the compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method. The search for an adequate and stable physical object or phantom solution is discussed in Section 5.4.

5.3. Review on interfacial pressure and compression transfer *in-vivo*

The pressure transfer from the bladder to *in vivo* soft tissues and vein structures is complex; therefore, direct correlation between compression ultrasonography bladder pressure and venous intraluminal pressure cannot be assumed. Instead, a phenomenological transfer function relates the interfacial pressure at the tissue surface to the intraluminal venous pressure. The bladder pressure is first absorbed by the soft tissues of the thigh and should not be directly equated to the venous pressure of the individual. Several studies emphasize the importance of considering interfacial pressure in this context. For example, Ye (2023)¹¹, numerically analyzed stress transmission from the skin to deeper tissues of the lower limb to optimize elastic compression stockings. The biomechanical properties of soft tissue in the human thigh remain an active area of research¹². Clinical investigations involving tourniquet application have highlighted the decrease in pressure as it propagates through thigh tissues. Cadaveric studies show that pressure transfer in thighs with smaller circumference (less than 40 cm) is nearly direct (transfer ratio above 0.9). However, for larger thighs (greater than 58 cm circumference), the pressure transfer ratio can drop below 0.7. Shaw (1982)¹³ published a nomogram relating tourniquet pressure to underlying tissue pressure and thigh circumference, demonstrating that pressure transfer is more attenuated in larger thighs. This phenomenon of pressure attenuation has led to the development of integrated monitors aimed at improving the placement of emergency tourniquets¹⁴. An experimental study by Hatt (2023)¹⁵ using magnetic resonance elastography quantified the nonlinear viscoelastic properties of adipose tissue and gluteal muscles *in vivo* to better

¹¹ Chongyang Ye, Rong Liu, Michael T.C. Ying, Fuyou Liang, Yu Shi, Characterizing the biomechanical transmission effects of elastic compression stockings on lower limb tissues by using 3D finite element modelling, *Materials & Design*, Vol. 232, 2023, 112182, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112182>.

¹² Justin Scott, Sheng Chen, Sara Roccabianca, Tamara Reid Bush, The effects of body position on the material properties of soft tissue in the human thigh, *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials*, Vol. 110, 2020, 103964, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2020.103964>.

¹³ Shaw JA, Murray DG. The relationship between tourniquet pressure and underlying soft-tissue pressure in the thigh. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1982 Oct;64(8):1148-52.

¹⁴ Nguyen JQ, Goss A, Keshishian H, Berchard F, Parks J, Evans C. TiMON: a real-time integrated monitor for improving the placement and wear of emergency tourniquets. *BMC Emerg Med.* 2025 Jan 6;25(1):4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12873-024-01169-6>.

¹⁵ Hatt A, Lloyd R, Bolsterlee B, Bilston LE. Strain-dependent shear properties of human adipose tissue *in vivo*. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater.* 2023 Jul;143:105924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2023.105924>.

understand how external loads transfer to underlying anatomy (muscle, fat, and bone). Lattimer (2014)¹⁶ discussed the relationship between external pressure and luminal pressure, noting the lack of clarity regarding its impact on venous disease. Flour (2011)¹⁷ addressed the variable effects of external compression on deep veins.

Interestingly, a linear increase in thigh cuff pressure does not correspond to a linear decrease in venous cross-sectional area at pressures below 40 mmHg. Factors such as patient positioning¹⁸ and vein depth/location of the vein¹⁹. Studies by Partsch (2002)²⁰ using transparent acetate windows in compression cuffs for duplex ultrasound access have shown that thigh pressures exceeding 40 mmHg are generally required to significantly reduce the diameter of the femoral vein. This suggests that considerable hydrostatic, abdominal, and tissue forces oppose compression and must be overcome before venous return is notably impaired.

Narracott (2009)²¹ demonstrated that changes in calf cross-sectional area measured by magnetic resonance imaging were large compared to the deep vessel cross-sectional area, implying that errors in assessing changes in deep vessel lumen using such methods may also be significant.

Therefore, initial pressure adjustment tailored to each individual is essential for the effective functioning of an automated compression ultrasonography method.

5.4. Compression and reaction results in tissue mimicking material with a vessel model

The evaluation of vein response to compression is performed through the thigh tissues, making the biomechanical properties of these tissues critical when selecting a surrogate phantom for compression ultrasonography. Here, *in-vivo* CDUS data from healthy volunteers are compared with data from tissue-mimicking materials and a vein model. Uniform testing of the CDUS method in intermittent operation requires a stable physical object—meaning one that consistently responds to repeated compressions from the wearable actuator module (WAM) with the electronic actuator controller (EAC).

A physical object with a compression response similar to that of a human subject was sought and acquired as a commercial physical phantom. A professional ultrasound phantom (3B Scientific, Hamburg, Germany)²² was obtained to ensure uniform testing across 10 compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) subsystems dedicated to the ThrombUS+ project. The testing setup is depicted in Figure 23.

¹⁶ Lattimer CR, Azzam M, Kalodiki E, Xu XY, Geroulakos G. Hemodynamic changes in the femoral vein with increasing outflow resistance. *J Vasc Surg Venous Lymphat Disord.* 2014 Jan;2(1):26-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvsv.2013.06.002>

¹⁷ Flour M, Clark M, Partsch H, Mosti G, Uhl JF, Chauveau M, et al. Dogmas and controversies in compression therapy: report of an International Compression Club (ICC) meeting, Brussels, May 2011 [published online ahead of print June 21, 2012]. *Int Wound J.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-481X.2012.01009.x>

¹⁸ B, Partsch H. Calf compression pressure required to achieve venous closure from supine to standing positions. *J Vasc Surg* 2005;42: 734-8. Partsch B, Partsch H. Calf compression pressure required to achieve venous closure from supine to standing positions. *J Vasc Surg.* 2005 Oct;42(4):734-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2005.06.030>.

¹⁹ H, Mosti G, Mosti F. Narrowing of leg veins under compression demonstrated by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). *Int Angiol* 2010;29:408-10.

²⁰ Partsch H, Menzinger G, Borst-Krafek B, Groiss E. Does thigh compression improve venous hemodynamics in chronic venous insufficiency? *J Vasc Surg.* 2002 Nov;36(5):948-52. <https://doi.org/10.1067/mva.2002.127343>.

²¹ A. J. Narracott, G. W. John, R. J. Morris, J. P. Woodcock, D. R. Hose and P. V. Lawford, "A Validated Model of Calf Compression and Deep Vessel Collapse During External Cuff Inflation," in *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 273-280, Feb. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2008.2005964>.

²² Sonotrain Vein Model Replacement Block 1019652 P120 <https://www.universalmedicalinc.com/replacement-block-for-p120-sonotrain-vein-model.html>.

Figure 23. Tissue-mimicking phantom “3B SONOtrain VEIN” with an embedded blood vessel model in the setup for testing the CDUS method.

To clarify the adequacy of the in vitro phantom in replicating tissue responses, pressure-strain diagrams obtained from the phantom were compared to those from 30 healthy volunteers. Pressure-strain diagrams²³ are a common method for characterizing the stiffness of in vivo tissues. Therefore, both the thigh tissues of healthy subjects and the physical phantom were experimentally characterized, as shown in Figure 24.

The “SONOtrain Vein Model” is a rectangular block of silicon with dimensions of 50 × 180 × 225 mm. The single phantom’s transverse size is only 50 × 180 mm, which is too small to represent the circumference of a surrogate thigh. This thin phantom is overly sensitive to compression, as shown by the yellow bold line in the diagram. Two phantoms stacked in layers form a transverse size of 100 × 180 mm, which is closer to the size of a thigh. The corresponding response of this layered phantom is shown by the purple bold line (Figure 24).

In the time-pressure diagram (Figure 24; left), a similar pressure increase is observed in both in vivo cases and the “SONOtrain Vein Model” phantom. Likewise, the pressure-strain diagram (Figure 24; right) shows a comparable increase in strain as the compression pressure rises in the bladder applied to both the in vivo tissue and the phantom.

The combined representation of induced pressure and tissue response, comparing in vivo tissues and the phantom, is presented in the pressure-strain diagram (Figure 25).

²³ Griffin M, Premakumar Y, Seifalian A, Butler PE, Szarko M. Biomechanical Characterization of Human Soft Tissues Using Indentation and Tensile Testing. *J Vis Exp.* 2016 Dec 13;(118):54872. <https://doi.org/10.3791/54872>.

Figure 24. Composite family of in-vivo registered features alongside features from the professional phantom "SONOtrain Vein Model 1019652 P120". Phantom responses are depicted with bold lines.

Figure 25. Recommended body positioning for the compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method (left) and joint representation of induced pressure and observed response diagrams (right) registered *in-vivo* from healthy subjects compared to a tissue-mimicking phantom. The yellow line represents the response.

The repeated recording of responses from silicon in phantom was also explored. The compression induction diagrams, and silicon responses are provided in Figure 26.

Figure 26. Results of monitoring trial on “SONOtrain Vein Model” phantom. Left: time-pressure diagram showing the rate of pressure increase. Right: pressure-strain diagram showing silicon response to compression.

The laboratory testing of CDUS functioning was repeated for a duration of 32 minutes, during which 20 compression sessions were performed on the “SONOtrain Vein Model” phantom. The 10 × 22 cm rectangular air bladder in the wearable actuator module (WAM) was inflated with air from the electronic actuator control (EAC). The EAC controller powered a piezoelectric air pump with 1400 mW output, inflating the bladder to a target pressure of 120 mmHg. The silicon phantom responses, expressed as pressure-strain diagrams (Figure 26; right), has the same repeatability as the pressure-time diagrams representing the compression cycles. The family of pressure-strain curves shows the same spread and consistency as time-pressure curves.

The “SONOtrain Vein Model” is a soft silicon block embedded with three hollow channels that imitate blood vessels. These channels have diameters of 4 mm, 8 mm, and 15 mm and are located 35 mm below the surface. In the ultrasonography B-mode image, only the 15 mm channel is visible. Manual manipulation of the imaging transducer on the phantom and the recorded strain data are shown in the photos in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Example of phantom ultrasonography using VERMON’s transducer. The by-hand compression level is observed on the phantom’s deformed surface, and the representative tissue reaction diagram is shown in the CDUS method’s experimental graphical user interface (GUI). Left: transverse view of the vessel model. Right: axial view of the vessel model.

Using the prototyped CDUS probe, the captured sequence of compression ultrasonography images from the phantom was analysed offline. The bladder was pressurized up to 100 mmHg over 25 seconds (Figure 28; top). During the CDUS session, a total of 300 frames were collected. Specific frames were selected at pressures of 22, 32, 51, 80, and 99 mmHg, corresponding to frame indexes 27, 45, 84, 148, 217, and 267. The six images depicting the vein model’s response to compression are shown in Figure 28;bottom.

Figure 28. Results of compression ultrasonography session on phantom. Top: selected frames from the sequence at predefined pressure levels (22, 32, 51, 80, and 99 mmHg). Stems on the time axis indicate the moments when these frames were captured. Bottom: selected ultrasonography frames showing the model lumen cross-section. The model lumen responds with a decrease in vertical size and lumen area.

The reactions of the vein model were characterized by the vertical size and area of the lumen. The vertical and horizontal sizes of the lumen were estimated manually by indicating the corresponding edges. From these measurements, the lumen area was calculated by approximating it as an elliptical shape. The profiles of lumen decrease are illustrated in Figure 29, showing the vein model’s response to seven compressions, each with a maximum pressure of 120 mmHg. These compressions were repeated seven times over a period of 10 minutes.

Figure 29. Profiles of lumen area decrease during seven compression sessions of the vein model.

In each compression session, the initial lumen area was estimated and assumed as the baseline size for that session. All subsequent measurements showed smaller sizes, so all captured images at increasing pressures provide data on the decreasing lumen area of the model. Therefore, negative percentage changes are indicated in Figure 29. At 120 mmHg bladder pressure, the lumen area of the model decreased by approximately 70% to 90%. The repeatability of the vein model’s response was assessed using the average and standard deviation, which are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Average and spread of responses of the lumen in the model vein.

Pressure (mmHg)	22	32	52	80	99	120
Area change average, %	0	-13	-37	-52	-67	-83
Area change std., %	0	7	8	3	6	6

The area estimation described here was performed by manually indicating the edges of the lumen pattern in the vein phantom images and approximating the area as an ellipse. Automated segmentation of the model lumen in the images, with pixel counting in the segmented mask (rather than elliptical approximation), will provide a more precise area estimation. These future improvements will be implemented in the Central Intelligence Hub (CHI).

Functions of CDUS hardware on phantom are tested using experimental graphical user interface (GUI). Real-time indexing example of sonography images (frames) and corresponding pressure readings in the bladder are provided in Figure 30. In this example the experimental graphical user interface (GUI) is commanded to pressurize bladder to 120mmHg. The current pressure readings are indicated in numerical "#PRESS, 119.520000, 118.470005" indicator (Figure 30). The pressure readings are collected from the initiation of the compression session and are plotted as a time series, as time goes by. The increase of pressure in the first 100 readings is clearly visible, resulting the air pumping into the bladder (Figure 30; top). The further two hundreds pressure samples indicate an almost constant pressure maintenance by the electronic actuator control (EAC) during the session, keeping pressure at about 120 mmHg.

Figure 30. Example data displayed in the experimental GUI of the CDUS method during phantom compression with 120 mmHg pressure. Top: the “Pump controls” tab is dedicated for the electronic actuator control (EAC) adjustment. Bottom: the “Beamformer controls” tab is dedicated for adjusting and controlling the ultrasound module (USM).

The corresponding diagram about phantom response is presented in the “Beam-Former Control“ tab (Figure 30; bottom). The strain (%) parameter is calculated from data of each ultrasonography image (frame), so three hundred tissue-strain measurements are presented in the diagram. The strain estimates are saturated after the first hundreds of samples as the pressure was kept constant in bladder, applying a constant pressure on the phantom. The ultrasonography image is updated continuously in the experimental graphical user interface (GUI). In the indicative example of Figure 30, the deformed pattern of the model’s lumen is observed, indicating the response to a pressure of 120mmHg by the wearable actuate module.

The implemented function of dosed compression to phantom silicon is illustrated with example data in experimental graphical user interface (GUI). As the option of non-AI (ML model) based control of compressing

is implemented²⁴ with thresholding on strain parameter. Pressurising of bladder is automatically monitored up to particular level of reaction in phantom. The example on experimental graphical user interface (GUI), when selected 8% strain threshold, is presented in Figure 31.

Figure 31. Example data displayed in the experimental GUI of the CDUS method during dosed compression of phantom. Top: in “Beamformer controls” tab, the strain threshold is set 8%. Bottom: the “Pump controls” tab indicates the progress of applied pressure, until phantom reaction reaches the set threshold.

In the case of automated dosing of compression, the pressurising is cancelled, and air from bladder released, when strain parameter reached the threshold. In Figure 31; top, it is observed that the strain estimates stopped rising when reached about 8%. The corresponding pressure peak reached a pressure of 39mmHg and the control to start pumping returned to status “Quick SET”. In this case of dosed compression with less

²⁴ Jurkonis R., Eitminavičius R., Marozas V. and Sakalauskas A. (2025). Automating Compression Ultrasonography of Human Thigh Tissue and Vessels via Strain Estimation. In Proceedings of the 18th International Joint Conference on Biomedical Engineering Systems and Technologies - Volume 1: BIOIMAGING; ISBN 978-989-758-731-3, SciTePress, pages 239-245. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0013264300003911>.

pressurised bladder the ultrasonography image showed less deformed pattern of model's lumen (see B-mode image on left part of the experimental GUI).

5.5. Discussion on the CDUS method characterisation results

Integrating the initial prototypes for implementing the compression duplex ultrasound method, the technical feasibility of compression ultrasonography was evaluated in preclinical settings. The dedicated ultrasound transducer developed by VERMON and the dedicated ArtUS Compact beamformer from TELEMED, were integrated into a C-shaped semi-rigid wearable (CSW) provided by ComfTech. KTU contributed the air pumping prototype (called EAC) to pressurize the bladder in the thigh-mounted CSW.

In the preliminary trials, the air-pumping electronic actuator controller (EAC), the air bladder together with TELEMED's transducer were capable of inducing thigh tissue compression. Thigh tissue compressions in healthy subjects were adequate according to vein lumen responses, which were visually observed in real time and manually measured offline. Full collapse of the lumen area was found in the recorded image sequences. Automated compressions were adequate in the group of healthy subjects. Assuming the same range of thigh circumferences in patients suspected for deep vein thrombosis (DVT), it is highly likely that automated compression with the ThrombUS+ device would be possible for 61% of the patient group. This estimate assumes a thigh circumference range from 46 cm to 59 cm.

Due to variability in the *in-vivo* tissue responses, uniform testing of the CDUS method presents challenges. The problem lies in the availability of reference objects adequate for evaluating and characterizing the performance of the compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method-implementing system.

This issue was addressed by acquiring a professional phantom made of tissue-mimicking material embedded with a vessel model. The stable biomechanical properties of the acquired "SONOtrain Vein Model 1019637/P120" (3B Scientific GmbH, Germany) were tested and deemed sufficient for final characterization of the CDUS method modules. A stable phantom will ensure uniform testing of CDUS method-implementing modules before delivery to clinical partners.

The recommended body positioning for CDUS sessions is supine with the back elevated at 30 degrees, commonly referred to as the low Fowler's position in medical practice. Other body positions should be avoided, as involuntary leg muscle activity can alter compression transfer through tissues, making it difficult to detect changes in vein response. In a fully relaxed thigh, compressions with a constantly pressurized bladder provide a practical solution for monitoring vein clinical status.

Special attention should be given to the specific effects of pressure transfer through soft tissues to the vein. Inflation with air builds pressure inside the bladder, which induces interface pressure on the skin; however, the effective pressure acting on the vein is always less than the bladder pressure. Trials with the WAM prototype and a 10 x 22 cm bladder on 30 healthy subjects showed adequate compression with bladder pressures up to 130 mmHg. The maximum capability of the WAM prototype is 140 mmHg, which is limited by the firmware.

Initial experiments highlighted design shortcomings in the C-shell semi-grid wearable (CSW), the ultrasonic transducer enclosure, and the fixation of the ultrasonic transducer into the handle. Through iterative redesign, partners communicated proposals (see Annex 1). These redesigns were discussed, and partners agreed on modifications to the CSW, ultrasonic transducer enclosure, and handle for manual manoeuvring during by-hand sessions.

6. Final conclusions of the deliverable

Probes developed by VERMON and FRAUNHOFER were integrated with the beamformer developed by TELEMED (at the physical and software levels). Beamformer parameters were selected according to the characteristics provided by the manufacturers of the probes.

Image quality assessment and optimization of the beamformer parameters were accomplished. Image quality assessment was performed using certified tissue and blood flow mimicking phantoms. Measured quantities and characteristics: spectral properties, axial and lateral resolutions, contrast resolution and sensitivity. Beamformer parameters tuning with the probes was performed in two iterations and image quality was slightly improved according to measurement results.

Technical feasibility demonstrated: Initial prototypes integrating the dedicated developed ultrasound transducer, beamformer, and wearable compression system successfully achieved adequate thigh tissue compression and vein lumen response in healthy subjects. This confirmed the technical feasibility of compression ultrasonography with the ThrombUS+ prototypes.

Design improvements: Initial testing revealed design limitations in the wearable compression system, transducer enclosure, and fixation method. Collaborative iterative redesign efforts among partners have led to modifications that improved device usability and performance before clinical trials.

Annex 1 – Mountings for the Linear Array PZT probes

To enable the use of the probe for training data collection via Study B1, where the experimental ThrombUS+ probe is planned to be used by an expert, hand-held mounting options were designed based on the following considerations

- One groove on opposite sides of the transducer is easier to clean than having 10 or more on each handle. The same applies to the semirigid C-shell (CSW) of the wearable actuator module (WAM).
- The groove also acts as a mechanical slide/support, preventing the transducer from falling out of the C-shell (CSW) during use.
- The handle may be designed for one-time use (to be disposed of afterward), but the WAM’s C-shell (CSW) is intended for reuse across many automated compression ultrasonography sessions on multiple patients.
- If a semi-soft inlay is used (for gel spread protection) between the transducer and the WAM’s C-shell, a wider groove attachment area will provide greater stability.

The hand-held mounting designs are shown in Figure 32 while the manufactured hand-held mounting is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 32. Design for the hand-mounting for the linear ultrasound array transducer.

The first This design did not include fixation features such as guiding grooves.

Figure 33. VERMON’s team 3D design of the probe handle, featuring a box-shaped slot (left) to fix the unchanged enclosure of VERMON’s linear array transducer (right).

The fixation option (Figure 32B) was evaluated in the context of fixation within the C-shell type semirigid wearable and during mounting on the human thigh. The redesign of the C-shell type semirigid wearable was iterated in collaboration with the wearable design partner, ComfTech, as shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35.

Figure 34. Design of the CSW with the ultrasonic imaging plane inclined at an angle of 20 degrees.

Figure 35. Based on experimental results, the C-shell type semirigid wearable was redesigned to include a soft insert and semi-flexible parts of the applicator.

With the redesigned entrance into the C-shell, the transducer fixation into the integrated probe will reach near-professional quality. The grooves will guide both the insertion and the fixation process.

The air bladder offered from ComfTech with offset of tubing inlet allows comfortable application of WAM on the lateral side of thigh (Figure 36).

Figure 36. Air bladder (10 x 22 cm) with offset tubing inlet (OD Ø4 mm) for integration with the CSW to prepare the iterated prototype of the WAM.

The wearable actuator module (WAM) with the air bladder, the linear ultrasound array transducer by VERMON and the C-shell semirigid wearable (CSW), all together are assembled and depicted in the photos of the final compression duplex ultrasound (CDUS) method-implementing system (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Photos of the iterated WAM prototype. Top: WAM consists of two separate parts, each interfacing with electronic equipment. Bottom: WAM assembled with velcro, adjustable to fit the circumference of the human thigh.

The one part of WAM incorporates ultrasound linear array transducer, so multichannel coaxial cable is wired to beamformer. The second part of WAM incorporates the air bladder, so pneumatic tubing is connected to outlet of electronic pumping module called EAC. Both interfacing lines shall eventually be covered into a single hose for neat management of the wiring.